

Lucerna Manual # 1:

How to prepare digital images files for upload to Lucerna

(Version May 2018)

Thank you for your willingness to contribute image files to Lucerna – The Magic Lantern Web Resource!

In this manual, we give a short introduction with background information, explain the steps of preparing image files, and provide a table with specifications for digital images and file sizes. This manual starts from the assumption that you either already have digital images files of objects related to lantern heritage and culture or know how to produce them.

1. Background Information

What this manual is for

This manual explains how to prepare digital image files for upload to Lucerna – The Magic Lantern Web Resource.

It does not explain

- how to digitize lantern slides >> see the resource “How to digitize lantern slides”
- how to catalogue items in Lucerna >> see Lucerna manual # 2: “How to catalogue slides and slide sets in Lucerna”

Entries that can be illustrated

Lucerna offers the possibility to add image files for all main entities:

- Lanterns slides
- Lantern hardware (projection apparatus, light systems, carriers, ...)
- Persons (images of people related to lantern heritage and culture)
- Organisations (e.g. logos of manufacturers)
- Events (e.g. billboards announcing a lantern lecture)
- Locations (e.g. photographs of buildings)
- Texts (e.g. title pages of publications)

The function of digital images in Lucerna

The aim of Lucerna is to make objects of lantern heritage and culture known to interested people. Digital images are an important source of information.

Lucerna is a reference database. Lucerna publishes **metadata** (e.g. titles, information on manufacturers, years of publication, related texts and more) and **images of objects** (e.g. images of slides, magic lanterns, title pages of historical texts, photographs) held in private

and public collections. The catalogued and illustrated objects themselves are not owned by the institution hosting Lucerna or the Lucerna administrators.

Some owners of objects agreed to publish images of objects from their collection under the condition that the quality of the digital images is not sufficient for commercial purposes. This is the reason why Lucerna does not offer high quality images. For high quality images, we refer users to the institution indicated in the credit line underneath the digital image.

Conditions for adding images to Lucerna

A digital image can be uploaded to Lucerna under the following conditions:

- The image quality complies with the minimum requirements of Lucerna
- The entity that the image illustrates is catalogued in Lucerna
- The original item (the slide, the apparatus, the photograph) is out of copyright
- You have permission to publish the digital image, hold copyright or waived copyright

2. Steps for Adding Images to Lucerna

The steps for adding images to an entry in Lucerna are described in detail below.

The steps are

- Step 1: Produce digital images
- Step 2: Name the image file according to the Lucerna ID numbers
- Step 3: Choose a credit line and license for the digital file
- Step 4: Transfer the files to the Lucerna administrator

Step 1: How to produce digital images

You can produce digital images for Lucerna through either scanning or photographing as long as the results comply with the minimum quality standards:

- All digital images need to be clear, sharp, and well-exposed colour reproductions. Scans of black-and-white photographs, texts or logos may be done in colour or in black and white.
- The image file type should be JPEG for static objects and MPEG for moving objects.
- The resolution for all images (static or moving) should be at least 150dpi (see table below).
- Digital **images of slides** must show the whole of the slide (i.e. not just the image area) and be cropped to the edges of the slide with a margin of 0-2 mm. A reproduction of a slide should document the binding or frames entirely, even when this increases white margins. The background area will be larger if it needs to show handles, levers etc. Good reproduction of any labels or inscriptions on the mount, frame or binding strips is desirable – either in one image or in several images of the same slide (see Fig. 1-2).

- Digital **images of apparatus** should document the object in its entirety (see Fig. 3). Multiple images of details or from several perspectives are welcomed.
- Image sizes for digital images of slides in the most common formats are documented in the table at the end of the document.

Fig. 1-3. *Left: slide documentation complying with requirements Lucerna: the slide is visible in its entirety and shows labels. Middle: the reproduction of the screened image alone is not sufficient for documentation in Lucerna. Right: digital image of object should depict the object entirely. Image credits: Fig. 1-2: EYE Film Institute Netherlands CC0 2016, Fig. 3: Museum voor Hedendagse Kunst Antwerpen, © 2017 MuKHA.*

Step 2: How to name the image file

Every image file has to be linked to the right entry. File naming is based on the Lucerna ID number (7 digits) for the image subject, with a suffix letter in small caps. This allows up to 26 different images for each catalogue entry!

Examples: 5100977a.jpg for the main image of a slide, 5100977b.jpg, 5100977c.jpg etc. for other images (details of subject, alternative colorations, front/back views etc.). Please name your images in alphabetical order, except for the letters “i” and “t”).

Accuracy in naming the files is critical – the Lucerna web pages are coded to pick up file names based on the ID numbers pulled out of the database.

Fig. 4-5. Example of the same commercially produced slide that exists in several executions. Both items – the coloured and the black-and-white slide – are connected to the same Lucerna ID number (5100977) but have different names for the digital image files: the file name of the coloured version (left) is 5100977a.jpg, the file name of the black-and-white version (right) is 5100977b.jpg. Additional digital images could be added.

How to identify the Lucerna ID number

Identify the Lucerna ID number of the slide, person, or hardware for your digital image.

If you know the title of slide, person, or slide set, search the Lucerna database. The following gives an example for a slide:

Go to “slide” and search for the slide’s title, in this case it is “Die Rosengartengruppe” (see Fig. 6). Lucerna ID numbers are visible at the very bottom of each entry.

Search

Contact us

Slide sets

Slides

People

Organisations

Events

Locations

Hardware

Texts

Keywords

Collections

Die Rosengartengruppe

Slide 2 of [Die Wundervelt der Dolomiten](#) (lecture: Projektion für Alle, 24 slides, c.1907)
– Coloured version of slide

[Monochrome version of slide](#)

EYE Film Institute Netherlands – reproduced by permission.
Digital image © 2016 Sarah Dellmann – CC0 (no copyright).

Format:	standard glass slide: 3¼ inches (83mm) square
Type of image:	photograph of exterior location
Dimensions:	height 3.25 inches (8.3 cm), width 3.25 inches (8.3 cm) (all dimensions are nominal; individual examples of this slide may have varied slightly from these values).
Material(s):	glass / paper
Production process:	photography, on glass substrate
Collections:	Example in The Hecht Collection: Screen Archive South East (University of Brighton)
	Example in EYE Film Institute Netherlands
Lucerna ID no. 5100977	Record created by Sarah Dellmann. Last updated 4 October 2016

Fig. 6. The Lucerna ID number is visible in the bottom of the entries.

Lucerna ID numbers for individual slides start with 5, Lucerna ID numbers for images illustrating texts start with 4 and those for persons start with 6. The Lucerna ID number for this slide is “5100977”.

Tip: some commercially produced slides only show the title of the slide set, not the title of each individual slide. You can then search via “slide set” for the set’s title to see if an entry exists.

What to do when no entry in Lucerna exists that corresponds to your digital image

If the object or person you wish to illustrate with an image is not listed in Lucerna, you need to create a new record before you can link the image to it. This means that you have to create a database entry for the slide set, slide, hardware, or person.

Creating new entries (or modifying existing ones) requires a user account for Lucerna. Please contact us if you want an account to start cataloguing! The Lucerna manual # 2 “How to catalogue slide sets in Lucerna” and the information buttons visible once you logged in to Lucerna will guide you through the process of creating entries.

Step 3: Choose a credit line and a licence for the digital file

Copyright law varies across countries. If you are the producer of the digital file you may have rights relating to the photograph or scan you created. You can choose between

- keeping copyright of the digital image. That would be the licence “copyright: your name” and grant Lucerna the non-exclusive publishing rights for display on the website
- waiving copyright of the digital image file by choosing a Creative Commons licence

Please note: if you keep copyright of the image, it is not allowed for people to re-use your image files without consultation. If you wish to allow people to create new works with your images, we suggest a CC0 licence. For more information, check the website of Creative Commons <https://creativecommons.org/choose/> or ask us if you have questions on licenses.

In addition, please choose a credit line. The credit line usually mentions the institution/collection that owns the *object* plus the licence and name of the producer of the digital image. Examples for credit lines are:

- Royal Albert Memorial Museum Collection – reproduced by permission.
Digital image © 2014 Royal Albert Memorial Museum and Art Gallery, Exeter.
- EYE Film Institute Netherlands – reproduced by permission.
Digital image © 2016 Sarah Dellmann – CC0 (no copyright).

Step 4: Transfer the files to the Lucerna Administrator

You cannot upload images directly to Lucerna, only administrators can. Please get in contact with the Lucerna team by clicking on the “Contact Us” form. This way, we can agree on how to transfer the image files. Small amounts of files may be sent as e-mail attachments; for large amounts of image files, free file transport services are available (such as Wetransfer, yousendit or others).

Once your image files are received by the administrators, they check and then upload the images including the credit line to the database. The administrator will also create smaller thumbnail files from the images you put online. As Lucerna is run by volunteers, this might not happen overnight. We will inform you once the images are online – feel free to check! If you have questions about this manual or find that things do not work, please contact us via the “contact us” form.

Thanks a lot for your contribution!

APPENDIX – Specification for Digital Images of Slides for Upload in Lucerna

Pixel figures shown in bold in the table are fixed to suit the Lucerna page layout; the others can be slightly flexible (+/- 5px) to account for variations in individual slides.

Slide dimensions are measured in the units most likely to have been used when they were made – inches for British and US manufacture, centimetres for most others. If you are unsure of the origin of a slide, use centimetres and measure to the nearest 0.1cm.

If your slide is not in the table below (which is still under construction and likely to be extended as more slide types are encountered), please contact us to define a size for the digital image.

In most cases the height of the slide is the more important and constant dimension (for example many toy slides were made to standard heights but different widths).

As a result the pixel figures shown in **bold** in the table below are fixed to suit the Lucerna page layout; the others can be slightly flexible (+/- 1%) to account for variations in individual slides.

There are two basic image sizes:

Main image. These are sized to reflect the relative sizes of different types of slides, based on a standard of 500px square for the 3.25 inch (83mm) standard European glass slide. Pixel sizes are calculated as 155 pixels (px) per inch of the slide dimension (61px per cm), rounded to the nearest 5px.

Thumbnail. These are a standard size of 80px high, with the width calculated to maintain approximately the same height:width ratio as found in the corresponding main image.

Thumbnail images are created by the Lucerna administration. You only need to send us image files in the main image format.

**APPENDIX - SPECIFICATION FOR DIGITAL IMAGES OF SLIDES FOR UPLOAD
IN LUCERNA (Continued)**

‘TOY’ SLIDES (the body dimensions are nominal – manufacture of these slides was often less accurate than other types)						
Slide body dimensions			Main image (px)		Thumbnail (px)	
Units	Width	Height	Width	Height	Width	Height
cm	11	3	675	180	300	80
cm	12.5	3	765	180	340	80
cm	13.5	3	825	180	360	80
cm	13	3.5	785	210	300	80
cm	15	4	910	240	300	80
cm	15.5	4	945	240	315	80
cm	16	4	975	240	325	80
cm	19	4	1155	240	385	80
cm	7	4.5	430	275	125	80
cm	16	4.5	975	275	285	80
cm	17	4.5	1035	275	300	80
cm	15.5	5	945	300	250	80
cm	17.5	5	1070	300	280	80
cm	20	5	1220	300	325	80
cm	23	5.5	1400	335	335	80
cm	19.5	6	1190	365	260	80
cm	24	6	1465	365	320	80
cm	28	6.5	1700	395	345	80
cm	20	7	1220	425	235	80
cm	22	7	1340	425	250	80
cm	27	7	1650	425	320	80
cm	24	8	1465	485	245	80
cm	30	8	1830	485	305	80
cm	28	9	1710	550	250	80
cm	30	10	1800	600	240	80
Inches	4	1	620	150	330	80
Inches	5	1.25	765	190	320	80
Inches	5.25	1.5	770	230	270	80
Inches	6	1.5	910	230	315	80

APPENDIX - SPECIFICATION FOR DIGITAL IMAGES OF SLIDES FOR UPLOAD IN LUCERNA (Continued)

WOOD-FRAMED AND OTHER LARGER SLIDES							
Slide body dimensions			Main image (px)		Thumbnail (px)		
Units	Width	Height	Width	Height	Width	Height	
cm	21	6	1280	370	275	80	
cm	42	13	2560	790	260	80	
cm	15	15	900	900	80	80	
Inches	10	2.75	1550	425	290	80	
Inches	6.9	3.7	1070	575	150	80	
Inches	6.75	3.9	1045	605	140	80	
Inches	7	4	1095	625	140	80	
Inches	13.5	4	2090	625	270	80	
Inches	14	4	2170	625	280	80	
Inches	15	4	2325	625	300	80	
Inches	17	4	2635	625	340	80	
Inches	8	5	1240	775	130	80	

STANDARD GLASS SLIDES							
Slide body dimensions			Main image (px)		Thumbnail (px)		
Units	Width	Height	Width	Height	Width	Height	
cm	8.3	8.3	500	500	80	80	
cm	10	8.3	600	500	100	80	
Inches	3.25	3.25	500	500	80	80	
Inches	4	3.25	600	500	100	80	
Inches	2.75	2.75	425	425	80	80	

Table: Image sizes for digital images of most common slide sizes. These are calculated as 154 pixels (px) per inch of the slide dimension (60.6px per cm), rounded to the nearest 5px.

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